

Cultural Significance and Infrastructure Challenges of Jayanti Devi Temple: A Geographical Perspective

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Accepted: 01 Dec 2025 / Published online: 31 Dec 2025

Abstract

Sacred places are spaces where one can connect with the divine and engage in religious activities. Sacred landscapes hold cultural, historical and spiritual significance, shaping the geographical and socio-economic fabric of regions. The Jayanti Devi temple, dedicated to the goddess Jayanti, situated on the foothills of the Shivalik ranges in Jayanti Majri village, Punjab, 15 kilometres from Chandigarh, is not just a site of worship rather it is a blend of history, faith and community life. This temple is a perfect example of how a sacred landscape shapes and is shaped by the culture, tradition, beliefs and everyday life. Analysing the information from field survey, interviews and oral narratives, the research revealed that the temple has evolved into a significant source of financial support for the surrounding region. The temple's cultural relevance is kept alive through a 2-day fair organised every year twice in the month of February and August, which transforms it into a vibrant centre of communal identity. Yet, challenges are faced like accessibility, transportation services, inadequate infrastructure and environmental degradation. This research aims to suggest some ways in which the temple's development can have a balance between tradition and growth.

Key Words: Sacred Landscape, Religious Tourism, Jyanti Devi Temple, Cultural Significance, Infrastructural Development, Communal Identity.

Introduction

Religious places have a profound impact on the culture, architecture and spiritual legacy of human civilization. Religious places often serve as a pilgrimage tourism with beautiful architecture, history, festivals, and music (Rani, 2024). Around the world, religious places like Pashupatinath Temple, Angkor Wat Temple and Mecca are visited not only for their spiritual significance but also for their architectural design and cultural beauty. Many temples are also visited for their scenic beauty; one of them, Siri Pada in Sri Lanka, is built on a mountain and surrounded by lush, forested hills (Bogahawatte, 2020).

India has been recognized as home to thousands of temples and sacred places that shape the cultural norms, architectural styles and local economies. Sacred places are deeply rooted in the Indian landscape, from ancient treasures like Kailasa Temple and Dwarkadhish Temple to revered shrines of Vaishnodevi and Kedarnath. These temples draw millions of visitors from far and wide every year and contribute to the economy. Tourists visit the temple because of two main factors i.e. sacredness and its image as tourist destination (Hermawam et al., 2016). Buddhist Jyanti Devi Temple is one of the classical examples of such places. It is an ancient temple which looks like a fort and is situated on the top of a mountain and maintained by the villagers (Thakur and Kala, 2023).

The temple is fifteen kilometres away from Chandigarh. It is named after the goddess of victory, one of Kangra Valley's seven goddesses. They are also known as the seven sisters, Naina devi, Jwalamukhi, Chintapurni, Mansa, Brajeshwari, Chaamunda and Jayanti devi situated in Himachal

Pradesh (Roy, 1998). Every day number of visitors visits this temple. But the increasing number of pilgrimages has changed the land use and caused rapid urbanisation. Road network influenced the growth with linear expansion. The increasing number of pilgrim and urban expansion has created challenges (Ascoura, 2013). Therefore, creating an information centre and museum is crucial to protect cultural heritage. These efforts can inspire people to appreciate and care for this sacred site ensuring its traditions, values and beauty are preserved as a legacy for generations to come (Deelaka Bogahawatte, 2020). Thus, sustainable and inclusive planning in heritage cities to balance tourism growth with cultural preservation and community welfare (Pati and Husain, 2023). Hence, present study is such an attempt in this regard to explore the cultural significance of the temple along with the infrastructural development.

Historical Narrative

The Jayanti Devi Temple, located in Jayanti Majri village, Punjab, near Chandigarh, was established around 600 years ago during the reign of Babar and it is one of the oldest temples and is dedicated to goddess of victory (Dhillon, 2016). At that time a small estate called Hathnore was situated at the north of Chandigarh. The king of Hathnore was a Hindu Rajput. The king had 22 brothers, one of them was engaged to the daughter of the king of kangra. The girl was great devotee of Mata Jayanti devi since her childhood. Every morning, she used to worship the goddess and only after that she would do other activities. When she was getting married, she was very anxious because for her it meant going far away from her deity and will not be able to have worship the goddess. Mata Jayanti devi was moved by the devotion of the girl. The goddess appeared in her dreams and promised to accompany her wherever she went.

A miracle occurred when the marriage procession departed from Hathnore with the bride's palanquin. Suddenly the palanquin became extremely heavy. It could not be moved by the king's troops. The bride then shared her dream with her father. In obedience to the divine's will, the king sent the goddess along with his daughter, set up another palanquin, and kept the idol inside. The

deity was followed by the priest and his family. On a hillside within his estate, the Hathnore king built a temple dedicated to the goddess. For 200 years, the daughter and later generations of the family worshipped the deity.

At that time, Mullanpur (now in Ropar) was a part the area that was under the control of a robber known as Garibdas or Garibu. Garibu established his reign by gradually seizing control of the Hathnore estate. The goddess could not tolerate the ill treatment towards her devotee and appeared in a dream of Garibu who was also a great devotee of the goddess. Inspired by the dream Garibu began the construction of the temple on a hillock which was later completed by his grandson Bhagwan Dass. The temple is run by two committees; one comprises of the family of priest and villagers of Jayanti Majri. The other committee is the residents of Mullanpur village.

Geographical Aspect

The temple situated on hill top have a picturesque landscape surrounded by lush green forest and wheat or rice fields. Four pillars in form of 9.8-foot octagonal columns and walls on all sides support the temple, which is built on a platform that is 6.10 meters high. The shrine faces southwest, and there is ample room for people to walk around the sanctuary, which is about five feet in circumference. The sanctuary is approximately 9 by 9 feet and has a square form, making it a Sandhara temple (Thakur et al., 2023). The stone idol housed within the sanctuary is sculpted.

The temple comprises of shrine of goddess Jayanti devi, a room and a kitchen for priest. There are idols of shiva, Ganesha, Lakshmi, and local deities Lokda dev and Bala Sundari in folk form. The temple attracts people from far and wide during a 2-day fair organised in February and August on Purnima (full moon). Jayanti devi dam, obscure but important, is situated next to Jayanti devi temple. It is essential for irrigation, flood control, and water management. The scenic beauty of the dam and its surrounding make it a potential spot for eco-tourism and recreational activities.

Map: 1

Location of Study Area

Source: Survey of India and google Earth Pro, 2025.

Figure: 1 (A)

Location of Jayanti Devi Temple and Jyanti Dam

Source: Google Earth Pro, 2025.

Figure: 1 (B)

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Objective

1. To examine the cultural significance of the temple.
2. To evaluate the accessibility and infrastructural Development of the temple.
3. To suggest the Sustainable tourism practices at the temple.

Research Methodology

The present study primarily based on the primary data collected through field survey, interviews and spatial mapping of the temple site. In Includes Interviews with residents, devotees and temple

authorities as well as observations on infrastructure and accessibility by using purposive sampling. While secondary data includes analysis of historical records and archival data, review of literature on sacred geography and religious tourism and Satellite imagery and GIS mapping for spatial analysis. Thus, a total of 200 responses has been collected through field survey. After data collection it will be processed and analysed thoroughly on Likert scale. Descriptive and thematic analysis of interview transcripts has been done thoroughly and the results of the study has been displayed through tables, bar graph, pie chart.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of Respondents

A total of 200 people were surveyed out of which 112 were males and 88 were females. Their age structure ranged from below 20 to above 50 and they follow different profession like housewife, students, self-employed, private job, government employee and farmer.

The age wise data shows that the people between age group 20-30 years are the largest segment, showing that young adults are most visitors. This is due to their mobility, scenic beauty of the temple, Jyanti Dam, spiritual interest and involvement in community activities

Figure: 02

Various Aspects of Mata Jyanti Devi Temple

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Figure: 02
Jayanti Devi Temple: Interaction with the visitors

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Cultural Significance

The survey indicated the tremendous religious and cultural significance of Jayanti devi temple among the community. The temple has a crucial role in cultural identity, communal life and spiritual rituals.

Figure: 01

Jayanti Devi Temple: Religious and Cultural Importance

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

The figure (01) shows that for 78% of the respondents, the temple has very important role in spiritual rituals, cultural identity and communal life. 18% respondents consider moderately significant, indicating that its worth is acknowledged, but to a lower degree. Only 4% respondents agreed for temple being nit important indicated that partially everyone agrees that the temple is relevant in some way.

Figure:02
Jyanti Devi Temple: Festival Celebrated

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

The figure (02) shows that Navratri (80 respondents said yes) is most celebrated festival in the Jayanti devi temple, indicating its strong cultural and community significance.

Figure: 03
Jayanti Devi Temple: Glimpse of Fair Organised On 11th And 12th February 2025

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

76 respondents identified local fair that it is equally important cultural activity organised at Jayanti devi temple. 24 respondents says that they have visited the temple on Diwali, Navratri and attended the local fair also. The figure concludes that Navratri the central festival and local fairs act as social bonding between the communities.

Accessibility And Infrastructure

Figure: 05
Jayanti Devi Temple: Mode of transportation used Visitors

Source:

Primary Field Survey, 2025.

The pie chart (figure: 05) shows that the majority respondents i.e. 80% commute to the temple by their own vehicle. 16% responded walking to the temple due to the proximity of local devotee. Only 4% respondents used public transport either due to limited availability or low preference for public commuting to the temple.

Figure: 06

Jayanti Devi Temple: Road connectivity

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Responses regarding the road connectivity to Jayanti devi temple shows different perspective in figure (06). 56 % of the total respondents considered road connectivity as average indicating that although the roads are functional but some issues are also there. 35 % responses regarding connectivity were good showing their satisfaction regarding the present condition of the road. Only 6 % respondents considered the road connectivity as excellent and 4 % respondents gave poor rating indicating that the road connectivity needs to be improved.

Figure: 07

Jayanti Devi Temple: Basic Facilities Available

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Plate: 5.1

Jayanti Devi Temple: Facilities Available

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025

The above chart shows the facilities which are available at the Jayanti devi temple complex. The observation and responses show that drinking water and shops for religious offerings are easily available. Toilet is available but there were few people who were not aware of that whereas there is a need to make space for accommodation and sitting area.

Plate: 5.2
Jayanti Devi Temple: Langar

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025

Figure: 07

Jayanti Devi Temple: Satisfaction level of Respondents

JHAM

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

Facilities Required and Challenges

Figure:08

Jayanti Devi Temple: Basic Facilities Required

JHAM

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

The survey reveals several challenges and requirements at Jayanti devi temple that need to be acknowledged for improvement of visitors' experience. The major concern reported by 44% respondents is the lack of adequate public transport services which indicated there is an urgent need to improve the transportation system especially for those who do not own private vehicle. 22% respondents emphasised the importance of safety and security and to provide secure and comfortable atmosphere for pilgrims. 21% respondents suggested for the improvement for road connectivity and 13% respondent said there was enough space for accommodation which indicates that more accommodation space need to be created.

Challenges

The pie chart shoes that the major environmental issue faced at Jayanti devi temple is littering (39%) which indicates that there is lack of proper waste disposal system. Another major issue is deforestation (31%) which may be caused by infrastructure development or unmanaged tourism

affecting natural surroundings. 30% respondents says that there is pollution around Jayanti devi temple which is air or noise pollution due to vehicles and crowd.

Figure:09

Jayanti Devi Temple: Basic Facilities Required

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

The above chart shows the role of community in maintaining the temple complex where the most contribution is through volunteering for cleanliness drive (74 respondents) indicating a high-level of environmental responsibility among the people. 54 respondents contribute through offerings and donation for maintenance providing financial support to the temple. 40 respondents show the communities participation in organisation religious event to preserve cultural and spiritual tradition.

Figure: 10

Jayanti devi temple: Community Initiative for Conservation and Management

Source: Primary Field Survey, 2025.

CONCLUSION

Jayanti devi temple is not just a hallowed place of devotion, but also a living example of faith, history, and communal life. Based on long-standing tradition the temple continues to meet the spiritual needs of its devotees while also creating the cultural identity of surrounding region. The yearly fair, festival such as Navratri and everyday rituals highlights how closely connected the temple is to people's common lives. It is more than just a religious structure; it is a centre for social connection, economic vitality, and cultural preservation. At the same time the issues faced such as restricted public transportation, inadequate infrastructure and environmental concern remind us of the delicate balance between dedication and progress. The words of local devotees and community members express both their deep pride in the temple and their desire for greater facility that respect the spaces purity. The community's active engagement in maintaining cleanliness paying maintenance and organising fair demonstrates that the temples future is in collective care.

Thus, the Jayanti devi temple is more than just a place to worship divinity; it is also a place where tradition, livelihood and community spirit comes together. Its story serves as a reminder that sacred places change throughout time yet continue to shape people's identities and aspirations. If managed carefully the temple has the potential to flourish as a centre of faith, culture, and sustainable tourism, maintaining its legacy while meeting the needs of future generations.

Policy Recommendations

To strengthen the temple's role as a sustainable spiritual and cultural hub, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Improvement of Public Transportation

- Provide special shuttle services, particularly on weekends and during festivals, from important cities like Chandigarh, Mohali, and Panchkula.
- Enhance current bus lines and last-mile connections to promote eco-friendly travel and lessen reliance on private automobiles.

2. Improvement of Roads and Infrastructure

- Give approach road resurfacing and widening priority, along with adequate street lighting and conspicuous signs.
- Create preparations for traffic control during the busiest festival seasons to ease traffic and guarantee the security of attendees.

3. Development of Accommodations

- To accommodate pilgrims from out of town, promote public-private partnerships (PPP) for the construction of eco-lodges, dharmshalas, and inexpensive guesthouses close to the temple.

- Encourage homestay programs to increase revenue and actively engage the neighbourhood.

4. Vendor support and market infrastructure

- Provide a specific area for the market where local sellers may set up permanent booths, storage spaces, and restrooms.
- To empower small company owners, offer training courses in digital payments, hospitality, hygiene, and product promotion.

5. Practices for Sustainable Development

- Install solid waste management measures, such as biodegradable bins and awareness campaigns, particularly during festivals.
- Utilize water collection and solar illumination to save operating expenses and your influence on the environment.

6. Promotion of Cultural Tourism

- Make multilingual information boards, audio tours, and tourism booklets that cover the temple's geography, history, and customs.
- To improve the cultural experience and lengthen visitor stays, plan heritage walks, folk performances, and handicraft exhibit during fairs.

7. Security and Emergency Services

- Boost CCTV surveillance, send out local volunteer teams, and set up first-aid centres for emergency medical and security support. Work with local police to maintain safety during high-foot traffic events.

8. Integrated Temple Management Committee

- Establish a Temple Management and Development Board comprising local stakeholders, government representatives, and heritage experts to oversee development without compromising spiritual values. Encourage community participation in policy decisions and implementation to ensure inclusivity and transparency.

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SOCIETY FOR
HERITAGE
ARCHAEOLOGY &
MANAGEMENT

Journal of Heritage, Archaeology & Management (JHAM) Volume 5 Issue II
E-ISSN: 2583-4126

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